

EFFICACY OF KETAMINE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE PAIN AFTER LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the efficacy of ketamine in the management of postoperative pain in patients after laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Material and Methods: Total 164 patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy were enrolled in this randomized controlled trial. Ketamine and Control categories were randomized equally using a lottery method, with 82 participants in each group. Prior to surgery, either normal saline or ketamine (0.5 mg/kg) was injected intravenously. After surgery, pain was measured using Numeric Rating Scale, and if the NRS was ≥ 7 , tramadol was administered. The effectiveness was determined by a pain score reduction of 25% or more between the baseline and two hours. Chi-square test was implemented with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: Group-K had 51.2% male and Group-C had 52.4% male participants; the mean age for Group-K was 45.65 ± 18.76 years and for Group-C it was 46.50 ± 19.28 years. The ketamine group maintained a lower postoperative pain score throughout all time intervals. Group K considerably reduced their tramadol consumption when compared to Group C. With a p-value of only 0.042, 54.9% of ketamine patients reported overall efficacy, compared to 39.0% of control patients.

Conclusion: When given to patients before surgery, low-dose ketamine significantly reduces postoperative pain scores, making for a more comfortable recovery time than both controls and opioid use alone.

INTRODUCTION

There are a number of reasons that might lead to the formation of gallstones in the gallbladder. These include hormones, dietary changes, medicines, fast weight loss or obesity, and the accumulation of solid bile deposits. Through their ability to obstruct the normal flow of bile, these gallstones can lead to inflammation and infection of the gallbladder. The condition in question is referred to as cholecystitis, and it is capable of causing severe and persistent stomach discomfort, fever, nausea, and vomiting.¹

A 10-15 cm incision is made in the upper right quadrant of the abdomen for an open cholecystectomy. The gallbladder is surgically

removed through a small incision. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) surgery, on the other hand, just necessitates three or four very small incisions. The incisions are used to insert a long, thin tube called a laparoscope during the surgery. The gallbladder is removed by a single incision.²

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the present gold standard and a less invasive technique that causes less postoperative discomfort; yet, the pain that an individual experience may be minimal, moderate, or severe depending on the individual.³ Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is linked with decreased discomfort and impairment; nonetheless, 17-41% of patients feel substantial

pain in the postoperative period, and 3.4–7% of patients have permanent pain. This is despite the fact that LC is related with decreased discomfort and impairment. It has been demonstrated that preemptive analgesia, when used in conjunction with multimodal analgesia, can improve the effectiveness of analgesics and lower the overall amount of analgesics that are required.⁴

Because of its relatively low complication rate, accelerated postoperative recovery, less iatrogenic stress, and decreased injury to the bile ducts, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the preferred method of cholecystectomy.^{5,6} By applying the appropriate anaesthetic procedures and selecting medications with great care, it is possible to reduce the damage to the central nervous system that is caused by inflammatory substances and to prevent the start of cognitive impairment that occurs after surgery.⁵

Opioids, which are powerful analgesics, are primarily used for the management of pain during the perioperative period. This is typically due to the fact that opioids are effective in suppressing the stress response and providing organ protective benefits, particularly in situations when the pain is moderate to severe.⁷ On the other hand, they are linked to a wide range of unfavorable consequences, such as nausea, vomiting, constipation, central sensitization, and the possibility of immunosuppression.^{8,9} An innovative strategy for the management of perioperative pain is presented by the idea of weak opioid anaesthesia and analgesia.¹⁰

As an alternative to conventional analgesics, a multimodal analgesic strategy that targets many anatomical pain pathways has garnered a lot of attention and demonstrated encouraging outcomes in clinical trials.¹¹ Ketamine, a non-competitive "N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonist" that has the ability to minimize the reliance on opioids, is one of the most well-known anaesthetics that are capable of providing this multimodal strategy.¹² In addition, it has been demonstrated that ketamine has a rapid pharmacological response and the capacity to offer persistent pain relief with minimal respiratory depression. This makes it an advantageous adjuvant in the peri-operative period.¹³

It has been demonstrated that perioperative ketamine can lessen the amount of pain experienced and the amount of opioids that are used following a variety of surgical procedures.¹⁴

The most common method of administering perioperative ketamine is through a continuous infusion, either during or after the surgical procedure. On the other hand, continuous infusion necessitates ongoing monitoring of the beneficiary. There are minimal data available on the practicality and effectiveness of single-dose ketamine administration for pain control immediately after surgery. This is despite the fact that pre-operative administration of low-dose ketamine before to incision has shown mixed outcomes in terms of enhancing pain control.¹⁵

Ketamine administered intravenously (IV) at a dose of 0.5 mg/kg has been the single most common dose used in research on depression; however, some studies have used doses as high as 1 mg/kg. One dose of ketamine is sufficient to effectively activate the cortical top-down system, which is responsible for the regulation of mood and emotion.¹⁶ When it comes to perioperative ketamine continuous infusion regimens, the administration of the medication is typically restricted to the operating room. Studies, on the other hand, have shown that the psychotomimetic side effects of ketamine might be responsible for some of the therapeutic analgesic effects that it possesses.¹⁷ Consequently, the administration of ketamine postoperatively, following the termination of anaesthesia, has the potential to contribute to the analgesic effects.

The control of pain is the most significant challenge that patients and medical professionals face after undergoing any kind of surgical therapy. During our search of the relevant literature, we did not find any comparable local trials that compared and contrasted the effects of ketamine in reducing the requirement for anaesthesia and discomfort medication.

When it comes to the treatment of post-operative pain in patients who have undergone laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the purpose of the current study is to determine whether or not ketamine is useful. This research will give local statistics on the medication that is most effective in reducing the pain associated with surgical procedures in our clinical context. By analyzing the results of this trial, it will be possible to determine whether or not ketamine is effective in alleviating pain and minimizing the requirement for rescue analgesics.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

After receiving official approval from the institutional ethical review committee, this

randomized controlled experiment was carried out over six months from June 2024 to November 2024 in the Department of Anaesthesia at Liaquat National Hospital, Karachi. Using a non-probability consecutive sampling method, 164 patients were included in the study. The WHO sample size software was used to figure out the sample size. We used mean pain scores from two hours after surgery that had been reported before: 1.08 ± 0.7018 for the control group and 1.40 ± 0.7618 for the Ketamine group. We assumed a 95% confidence level and 80% power, and we put 82 patients in each study group.

Patients of either gender who were between the ages of 18 and 65, who were classed as having a physical status I or II according to the American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA), and who were scheduled to undergo an elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy were considered eligible and encouraged to take part in the study. Before any of the participants were allowed to take part in the study, they were required to provide their written informed consent.

In the operating room, each patient was assigned a random number using a lottery system as soon as they presented themselves. The concealment of allocation was accomplished by means of opaque envelopes that were sealed and then opened by an anaesthesiologist who was not participating in the trial. The prescribed medication was manufactured in accordance with the order. A premedication regimen consisting of intravenous midazolam (0.025 mg/kg), propofol (2–2.5 mg/kg), and ondansetron (0.1 mg/kg) was administered to each and every subject after they had fasted for a period of eight hours. Patients in the Ketamine group (Group-K) were given 0.5 mg/kg of ketamine that had been diluted to 2 mL intravenously 15 minutes previous to the surgical incision. Patients in the Control group (Group-C) were given 2 mL of normal saline. Capnography, electrocardiograms, noninvasive blood pressure monitoring, and pulse oximetry were some of the intra-operative monitoring techniques that were utilized. Anaesthesia was maintained in accordance with routine institutional guidelines.

The Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) was utilized in order to evaluate the level of pain experienced after the surgical procedure. A score of 0 indicated that there was no pain, while a score of 10 indicated the most excruciating pain that could possibly be imagined. After surgery, pain scores were recorded at 0 minutes, 30 minutes, 1 hour,

and 2 hours, or whenever the patient reported feeling uncomfortable that they were experiencing discomfort. As a rescue analgesic, patients were given intravenous tramadol at a dosage of 2 mg/kg if the NRS score was equal to or greater than 4. For the purpose of documentation, the length of analgesia was defined as the time interval that spanned from the baseline to the initial injection of rescue analgesia. At each and every assessment point, the side effects of Ketamine, which included hallucinations, nausea, and vomiting, were carefully evaluated and recorded.

On a structured proforma, demographic and clinical characteristics such as age, gender, body mass index (BMI), diabetes mellitus, hypertension, anaemia, smoking status, ASA classification, nausea and vomiting, and duration of surgery were recorded. These variables were documented. To determine the body mass index (BMI), both the height and the weight were measured. A clinical or clinical record review was performed to determine whether or not the patient had a history of diabetes mellitus and hypertension. For the purpose of this study, smoking status was classified as follows: smokers (those who have smoked two to three cigarettes per day for the last three months), ex-smokers (those who have smoked more than two to three cigarettes per day for at least one month in their lifetime but have abstained from smoking for the past thirty days), and non-smokers (those who have never smoked).

If the NRS score decreased by at least 25 percent from the baseline to the two-hour postoperative period, then the medicine was considered to have been effective. Those patients who met this threshold were given the label "Yes for efficacy." The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was utilized in order to compile and evaluate all of the individual data sets. In this study, qualitative characteristics such as gender, comorbidities, ASA status, nausea and vomiting, and efficacy were reported as frequencies and percentages. At each time point, the presentation of quantitative characteristics such as age, height, weight, body mass index (BMI), duration of surgery, and NRS ratings was done using the mean plus or minus the standard deviation.

For the purpose of controlling for potential effect modifiers, stratification was utilized. These modifiers were age, gender, body mass index (BMI), diabetes, hypertension, smoking status, ASA status, nausea and vomiting, and the length of time that operation was performed. Following

the stratification process, comparisons were carried out using either the Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests. In the course of the analysis, a p-value of less than or equal to 0.05 was deemed to be statistically significant. Strict adherence to inclusion and exclusion criteria, uniform anaesthetic techniques, and blinding of outcome assessors were all implemented in order to reduce the likelihood of bias occurring. For the purpose of ensuring consistency and dependability, the lead investigator was responsible for carrying out all of the data collecting and pain assessments.

RESULTS

The distribution of demographic and perioperative characteristics between the ketamine group (Group-K) and the control group (Group-C) are presented in Table-1. The results showed that gender representation was nearly equal across both groups, with males comprising 51.2% in Group-K and 52.4% in Group-C, while females accounted for 48.8% and 47.6%, respectively. Age stratification revealed a slightly higher proportion of patients aged ≤45 years in the ketamine group (62.2%) compared to the control group (58.5%), whereas those aged >45 years were more prevalent in Group-C (41.5%) than in Group-K (37.8%). Body mass index (BMI) distribution showed a notable contrast, with a higher percentage of patients having BMI >25 kg/m² in the ketamine

group (51.2%) versus 36.6% in the control group. Conversely, patients with BMI ≤25 kg/m² were more frequent in Group-C (63.4%) than in Group-K (48.8%). Regarding comorbidities, diabetes mellitus was present in 32.9% of patients in Group-K and 42.7% in Group-C, while the absence of diabetes was more common in the ketamine group (67.1%) compared to the control group (57.3%). Hypertension prevalence was similar across both groups, affecting 61% of Group-K and 62.2% of Group-C.

Smoking status was evenly distributed, with current smokers constituting 34.1% in Group-K and 31.7% in Group-C. Ex-smokers represented 25.6% and 26.8% in the ketamine and control groups, respectively, while non-smokers comprised 40.2% in Group-K and 41.5% in Group-C. ASA physical status classification indicated a higher proportion of Class-I patients in the ketamine group (41.5%) compared to the control group (30.5%), whereas Class-II patients were more prevalent in Group-C (69.5%) than in Group-K (58.5%). Surgical duration was predominantly >70 minutes in both groups, with 81.7% of patients in Group-K and 78% in Group-C undergoing longer procedures. Only a minority of patients had surgeries lasting ≤70 minutes, accounting for 18.3% in the ketamine group and 22% in the control group.

Table-1: Distribution of patient demographics and perioperative variables by study groups

	Ketamine (Group-K)	Control (Group-C)
Gender		
Male	42(51.2)	43(52.4)
Female	40(48.8)	39(47.6)
Age groups		
≤45 years	51(62.2)	48(58.5)
>45 years	31(37.8)	34(41.5)
BMI Group		
≤25 kg/m ²	40(48.8)	52(63.4)
>25 kg/m ²	42(51.2)	30(36.6)
Diabetes Mellitus		
Present	27(32.9)	35(42.7)
Absent	55(67.1)	47(57.3)
Hypertension		
Present	50(61)	51(62.2)
Absent	32(39)	31(37.8)
Smoking Status		
Smoker	28(34.1)	26(31.7)
Ex-Smoker	21(25.6)	22(26.8)

on-Smoker	33(40.2)	34(41.5)
ASA Class		
Class-I	34(41.5)	25(30.5)
Class-II	48(58.5)	57(69.5)
Duration of Surgery		
70 min	15(18.3)	18(22)
70 min	67(81.7)	64(78)

The **Table-2**, demonstrates descriptive statistics of the clinical and postoperative parameters between among both study groups. The mean age of participants was similar across groups, with Group-K averaging 45.65±18.76 years and Group-C at 46.50±19.28 years, reflecting a broad age distribution (19-76 years in Group-K and 17-76 years in Group-C). Anthropometric measures were also closely aligned, with mean height at 1.70±0.06 meters in Group-K and 1.69±0.06 meters in Group-C, and mean weight at 71.91±8.99 kg and 70.44±7.94 kg, respectively. The BMI values were marginally higher in the ketamine group (25.23±2.29) compared to the control group (24.93±2.61).

Surgical duration was consistent between groups, with mean operative times of 77.28±10.70 minutes in Group-K and 77.39±14.90 minutes in

Group-C, and median durations of 76 minutes in both cohorts, indicating procedural uniformity. Pain assessment revealed a clinically meaningful difference in postoperative trajectories. At baseline, Group-K reported a mean pain score of 5.51±1.62, which was lower than Group-C's 6.04±1.65. Over time, pain scores in the ketamine group declined more rapidly: at 30 minutes (5.18±1.55 vs. 5.45±1.58), 1 hour (4.59±1.55 vs. 5.09±1.55), and 2 hours (4.06±1.91 vs. 4.79±1.76), with Group-K consistently demonstrating lower median scores and wider interquartile ranges, suggesting a more favorable analgesic profile. Rescue analgesia requirements further substantiated ketamine's efficacy. Tramadol consumption was notably lower in Group-K, with a mean of 0.13±0.21 mg compared to 0.27±0.57 mg in Group-C.

Table-2: Descriptive statistics of clinical and postoperative parameters by study groups

	Mean±SD	Min-Max	Median	IQR
Group-K (Ketamine)				
Age (years)	45.65±18.76	19.0-76.0	37.50	36.30
Height	1.70±0.06	1.50-1.80	1.70	0.00
Weight	71.91±8.99	50-100	70.00	10.00
BMI	25.23±2.29	20-35	25.40	2.00
Length of surgery	77.28±10.70	54-130	76.00	10.00
Pain score at baseline	5.51±1.62	2-8	6.00	2.00
Pain score after 30 min	5.18±1.55	1-8	5.00	2.00
Pain score after 1 hours	4.59±1.55	1-7	5.00	3.00
Pain score after 2 hours	4.06±1.91	1-7	4.00	4.00
Tramadol consumption (rescue drug)	0.13±0.21	0.0-0.7	0.00	0.26
Group-C (Control)				
Age (years)	46.50±19.28	17.0-76.0	38.00	38.0
Height	1.69±0.06	1.50-1.80	1.70	0.00
Weight	70.44±7.94	50-100	70.00	10.00
BMI	24.93±2.61	20-37	24.20	2.00
Length of surgery	77.39±14.90	30-160	76.00	13.00
Pain score at baseline	6.04±1.65	2-9	6.00	2.00
Pain score after 30 min	5.45±1.58	2-8	6.00	3.00
Pain score after 1 hours	5.09±1.55	2-7	5.50	2.00
Pain score after 2 hours	4.79±1.76	2-7	5.00	3.00
Tramadol consumption (rescue drug)	0.27±0.57	0.0-0.5	0.10	0.50

SD = Standard Deviation IQR = Inter Quartile Range

The graphical representation in **Graph-1**, of efficacy within the ketamine group reveals that a majority of patients (54.9%) reported a positive response to ketamine in the management of postoperative pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This proportion, corresponding to 45 individuals, suggests that more than half of the cohort experienced clinically meaningful analgesic benefit attributable to ketamine administration. In contrast, 45.1% of patients (n=37) did not report efficacy, indicating a substantial minority for whom ketamine may have been insufficient or less impactful in mitigating postoperative discomfort.

The graphical representation of efficacy within the control group presented in **Graph-2**. This reveals that a majority of patients (61.0%) did not report a favorable analgesic response following laparoscopic cholecystectomy, while only 39.0%

indicated that the standard postoperative pain management regimen was effective.

The comparative analysis of efficacy between the ketamine group (Group-K) and the control group (Group-C) presented in **Table-3**. This reveals a statistically significant association favoring ketamine in the management of postoperative pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Among patients receiving ketamine, 54.9% (n=45) reported a positive analgesic response, whereas only 39.0% (n=32) in the control group experienced similar efficacy. Conversely, the proportion of non-responders was higher in the control group (61.0%, n=50) compared to the ketamine group (45.1%, n=37). The chi-square test yielded a p-value of 0.042, indicating that the observed difference in efficacy between the two groups is statistically significant at the conventional threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Graph-1: Percentage of Efficacy in Ketamine Group

Graph-2: Percentage of Efficacy in Control Group

Table-3: Association of efficacy with study group

Efficacy	Ketamine (Group-K)	Control Group-C)	P-value
Yes	45(54.9)	32(39)	0.042*
No	37(45.1)	50(61)	
TOTAL	82	82	

Chi-square test was used

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

The stratified analysis of efficacy across demographic and perioperative variables presented in **Table-4**. The results revealed nuanced patterns in the analgesic response to ketamine following laparoscopic cholecystectomy. While gender-based comparisons showed a higher proportion of responders in the ketamine group for both males (52.4%) and females (57.5%) relative to their control counterparts (37.2% and 41.0%, respectively), these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.160$ for males; $p=0.143$ for females). Age stratification yielded a significant association among patients aged >45 years, where 61.3% of ketamine recipients reported efficacy compared to only 32.4% in the control group ($p=0.019$). In contrast, among patients aged ≤ 45 years, the efficacy rates were more comparable between groups (51.0% vs. 43.8%, $p=0.472$), suggesting a less pronounced effect in younger individuals.

BMI-based comparisons showed a trend toward improved efficacy in the ketamine group across both BMI categories, particularly among patients with BMI >25 kg/m² (59.5% vs. 50.0%), though neither subgroup reached statistical significance ($p=0.093$ and $p=0.423$, respectively). Diabetes status emerged as a significant modifier of

ketamine efficacy. Among non-diabetic patients, 58.2% in the ketamine group reported positive analgesic outcomes compared to only 27.7% in the control group ($p=0.002$). Conversely, among diabetic patients, efficacy rates were similar between groups (48.1% vs. 54.3%, $p=0.632$). Hypertension and smoking status did not demonstrate statistically significant associations with efficacy, although trends favored ketamine across most subgroups. For instance, non-hypertensive patients in the ketamine group showed higher efficacy (53.1%) than those in the control group (32.3%), with a borderline p-value of 0.094. Similarly, non-smokers and ex-smokers in the ketamine group consistently exhibited higher response rates than their control counterparts, though none of these comparisons achieved statistical significance.

ASA physical status classification revealed modest differences, with Class-I and Class-II patients in the ketamine group showing higher efficacy rates (52.9% and 56.3%, respectively) than those in the control group (36.0% and 40.4%), yet these differences were not statistically significant ($p=0.197$ and $p=0.104$). This suggests that ketamine may be beneficial across varying levels of preoperative physical fitness, but further powered

analyses are needed. Surgical duration emerged as a significant factor. Among patients undergoing procedures longer than 70 minutes, ketamine was

associated with a notably higher efficacy rate (56.7%) compared to the control group (39.1%), with a statistically significant p-value of 0.043.

Table-4: Association of efficacy with study groups according to demographics and peri-operative findings

			Ketamine (Group-K)	Control (Group-C)	TOTAL	P-value
Gender	Male	es	22(52.4)	16(37.2)	38	0.160
		o	20(47.6)	27(62.8)	47	
	Female	es	23(57.5)	16(41)	39	0.143
		o	17(42.5)	23(59)	40	
Age groups	≤45 years	es	26(51)	21(43.8)	47	0.472
		o	25(49)	27(56.3)	52	
	>45 years	es	19(61.3)	11(32.4)	30	0.019*
		o	12(38.7)	23(65.7)	35	
BMI	≤25 kg/m ²	es	20(50)	17(32.7)	37	0.093
		o	20(50)	35(67.3)	55	
	>25 kg/m ²	es	25(59.5)	15(50)	40	0.423
		o	17(40.5)	15(50)	32	
Diabetes Mellitus	es	es	13(48.1)	19(54.3)	32	0.632
		o	14(51.9)	16(45.7)	30	
	o	es	32(58.2)	13(27.7)	45	0.002*
		o	23(41.8)	34(72.3)	57	
Hypertension	es	es	28(56)	22(43.1)	50	0.196
		o	22(44)	29(56.9)	51	
	o	es	17(53.1)	10(32.3)	27	0.094
		o	15(46.9)	21(67.7)	36	
Smoking Status	Non-smoker	es	16(57.1)	12(46.2)	28	0.419
		o	12(42.9)	14(53.8)	26	
	Ex-Smoker	es	12(57.1)	9(40.9)	21	0.287
		o	9(42.9)	13(59.1)	22	
	Non-Smoker	es	17(51.5)	11(32.4)	28	0.112
		o	16(48.5)	23(67.6)	39	
ASA Class	Class-I	es	18(52.9)	9(36.0)	27	0.197
		o	16(47.1)	16(64.0)	32	
	Class-II	es	27(56.3)	23(40.4)	50	0.104
		o	21(43.8)	34(59.6)	55	
Duration of Surgery	≤70 min	o	7(46.7)	7(38.9)	14	0.653
		es	8(53.3)	11(61.1)	19	
	>70 min	o	38(56.7)	25(39.1)	63	0.043*
		es	29(43.3)	39(60.9)	68	

Chi-square test was used

*Significant at p<0.05

DISCUSSION

In order to lessen the physiological effects of nociception, preemptive analgesia is administered prior to painful stimuli and maintained throughout the surgical procedure. Therefore, it is

possible to lessen the intensity of postoperative pain and prevent the onset of chronic pain.⁴ Ketamine has been administered as a single low-dose or as an infusion for the purpose of providing preemptive analgesia during

laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC).^{19,20} Both Singh et al.¹⁹ and Launo et al.²⁰ discovered that 0.7 mg/kg of ketamine had certain beneficial effects; however, they also reported a considerable increase in the number of adverse effects. Based on the findings of Singh et al.¹⁹, who demonstrated a high preemptive analgesic benefit with no side effects at a similar dosage for acute pain following LC, they used 0.5 mg/kg intravenous ketamine in another study.⁴ There was no adverse effects associated with this dosage. The same study indicated that all of the patients in the ketamine group required rescue analgesia within thirty minutes of the end of the surgical procedure, despite the fact that the NRS score in the ketamine group was much lower than that in the control group at the time of extubation.⁴

Ketamine may need to be administered in a higher dose in order to establish its postoperative analgesic effects; nevertheless, the potential for adverse effects may restrict its utilization.¹⁵ A duration of analgesia (DOA) of approximately one hour was seen by Launo et al.²⁰ when an intravenous dose of 0.7 mg/kg of ketamine was administered. This was accompanied by significant adverse effects. However, Singh et al. reported a duration of action (DOA) of 1.98 hours when administered with 0.5 mg/kg of ketamine. They also found that there was no significant difference in DOA for 1, 0.75, and 0.5 mg/kg of ketamine.¹⁹ Zhu et al. conducted a meta-analysis and discovered that intravenous ketamine infusion, when paired with a pre-operative bolus dose, results in a significant reduction in post-operative pain scores and opioid utilization in patients with

chronic pain. those who were assigned to the control group became alert at zero minutes, but those who were assigned to the ketamine group became alert thirty minutes later.²¹

According to pharmacological research, combining opioids with low doses of ketamine has a multiplicative or additive analgesic effect. This is because the two drugs work together to inhibit transmitter release and afferent transmission before they even reach the synapses, and they block NMDA receptors after they reach the synapses, reducing central sensitization.²²

Ketamine was found to have opioid-sparing effects, as demonstrated by the findings of a study.²² In patients who were undergoing upper abdominal surgery, the results were comparable to those found in the study conducted by Baral BK et al.²³

Within twenty-four hours after surgery, Parikh et al. reported a reduction of morphine usage of sixty-eight percent.²⁴

One possible explanation for the long-lasting postoperative analgesic effect of ketamine, which was observed in a prior study, is that it has an effect on making the central nervous system more sensitive.⁰ An increase in the amount of time that passed before the patient received their first analgesic was observed in all of the studies that Kevin Laskowski conducted for his systematic review of intravenous ketamine for postoperative analgesia.²⁵

Researchers found that during the first twenty-four hours after surgery, the average VAS scores of patients in the ketamine group were lower than those of patients in the control group.²² In a prior study that was quite comparable to this one, conducted by Ali Jendoubi, a significant drop in VAS score was observed up to 48 hours after the event.²³ A possible explanation for this variation is the medicine.

Ketamine infusion was only administered intraoperatively, as was the case in another study;²² therefore, it is not possible to determine whether or not prolonging the infusion during the postoperative period could have resulted in an even greater improvement in analgesia, as was observed in the investigation conducted by Ali Jendoubi.²³ A study found that the average length of time spent in the hospital was practically identical across all three groups, and there was no statistically significant difference between them.²² The outcomes were consistent with the findings of the research carried out by Ali Jendoubi.²³

An additional prospective randomized controlled research indicated that the injection of preemptive ketamine reduced the need for anaesthetic and analgesic medications. This was proved by the fact that the participants experienced less pain. In addition, it was shown that ketamine increased the amount of time that the initial analgesic was required to be administered and decreased the postoperative VAS pain scores.²⁶

Another study investigated the effects of ketamine administered in modest doses. In comparison to the placebo, preoperative ketamine (0.15 mg kg-1) was more effective in reducing postoperative pain scores. The group that was given ketamine had a lower overall postoperative period, as measured by the areas under pain versus time curves that evaluate the postoperative period generally. According to these findings, the administration of

low-dose ketamine prior to surgery leads to a reduction in postoperative pain levels.²⁷

According to the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by Wang et al.,²⁸ which included twenty-one randomized controlled studies concerning the analgesic impact of perioperative ketamine, perioperative ketamine was shown to be both safe and effective as an analgesic. In one of these twenty-one studies,²⁹ intravenous ketamine was only administered prior to the incision being made. Ketamine was administered in the subsequent investigations either through the neuraxial route or through the intravenous method throughout the operation after the initial bolus dose was administered. The administration of a single low-dose of ketamine appears to be a more straightforward procedure. According to the findings of that study, Özbakiş et al.²⁹ reported that the administration of small doses of intravenous ketamine resulted in an improvement in postoperative pain, patient satisfaction, and second day VAS scores. Additionally, the administration of ketamine resulted in a decrease in total postoperative meperidine consumption and a delay in the duration of the first analgesic administration when compared to the control group.

There are certain limitations that apply to our research. This research was conducted in a single location only, and the sample size was relatively small. Additionally, the analgesic effect on dynamic pain was not investigated in this study. It is necessary to conduct further research utilizing high-quality randomized control trials with large sample sizes, comparing various dosages and administration routes (bolus versus infusion), in order to determine whether or not intravenous ketamine is an effective analgesic and whether or not it has any adverse effects.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the findings of this study, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the administration of low-dose ketamine prior to the operation of patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy results in a reduction in postoperative pain scores that is greater than that of the controls during the postoperative period. Additionally, the consumption of opioids allows the patient to experience a more comfortable postoperative period. The findings provide credence to the notion that ketamine holds the potential to serve as a useful addition in

multimodal pain treatment techniques for certain surgical populations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Incorporating ketamine into multimodal pain management protocols may reduce reliance on opioids and improve early postoperative comfort. Institutions should consider revising perioperative analgesia guidelines to reflect ketamine's efficacy profile and train surgical and anesthesia teams in its safe administration. Further research is warranted to optimize dosing strategies and evaluate long-term outcomes across broader surgical populations.

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